

BEST PRACTICE

This is part of a series of guidance documents produced by the NADIR FP7 project. There are various international and national standards in place for undertaking infectious work in animals with pathogens that require high containment facilities. These guidance documents be examples of how these can be practically interpreted

Emergency Procedures and Contingency Planning in Containment Facilities

1. INTRODUCTION

This Best Practice document describes the minimum requirements for dealing with events of certain major accidents within Containment Level 3 (CL3) animal facilities

2 EMERGENCY PLANS AND PROCEDURES

- 2.1 Regulations and good practice require plans to be in place to deal with accidents or incidents involving CL3 Animal Facilities. There needs to be procedures to be in place for responding to serious and imminent danger, e.g. fire or containment failure, to protect the health and safety of staff and minimise the impact on biosafety of the experiment and welfare of the animals. Risk assessment must identify all the readily foreseeable incidents to be covered by the procedures.
- 2.2 Emergency procedures must contain arrangements to ensure that the emergency services have sufficient knowledge of the risks within the facility.
- 2.3 The emergency plans and procedures must also document additional procedures if the incident occurs out of hours and/or when a member of staff may be lone working.

3 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES (SOPs)

- 3.1 SOPs must be in place and include the following:
- Procedures to be followed (refer to 3.3)
 - Identifying the roles and responsibilities of staff in the management of the response to the emergency, including the first point of contact
 - Training requirements
 - The safety equipment and PPE to be used
 - Arrangements for liaison with emergency services (if required)
 - Drill frequency and minimum attendance requirements (to work unsupervised in the unit)
 - Accident/incident reporting and investigation arrangements
 - First aid arrangements including occupational health and post exposure prophylaxis (if appropriate)
- 3.2 All facilities must have documented within an SOP procedures in the event of the following:
- Fire (actual and alarms)
 - Power failure - prolonged (both mains and back up generator failure)
 - Power failure - mains (generator back up working)
 - Spillage outside of primary containment (primary containment is generally the room in CL3 farm animal facilities)
 - Spillage inside of primary containment
 - Failure of primary containment
 - Alarms e.g. Air pressures, effluent treatment plants (ETP)
 - Fumigation vapour release, if applicable
 - Others as dictated by local procedures e.g. chemical spillages

3.3 Emergency procedures must consider and document the following:

- Evacuation procedures to be followed by employees e.g. removal of contaminated clothing, route and access to another containment facility if showering is required.
- Prevention of access to the facility, if door locking systems are disabled during alarms
- Emergency escape routes and assembly points
- Procedures to account for all employees after an emergency evacuation has been completed
- Procedures to be followed by employees performing fire warden and first aid duties
- Decontamination of facilities, if applicable
- Clean up and disposal of waste
- Individual(s) with responsibility for contacting the engineering support including arrangements to meet with the responding engineer and apprise them of the situation and for allowing re-entry into the building

4 ACCIDENT REPORTING AND INVESTIGATION

4.1 All accidents and near misses must be reported to the institute biosafety officer and managers responsible for the facility and a full accident investigation report must be completed as soon as possible.

5 PERSONNEL AND EQUIPMENT

5.1 First Aid

As a minimum all containment facilities must have:

- A suitably stocked first aid container
- A qualified first aider who has the necessary health clearance and is competent to enter the facility unsupervised
- Information on first aid arrangements, including contact details, displayed in prominent areas.

5.2 Fire Wardens

Each facility must be covered by a fire warden with suitable health clearance

5.3

Spill Kits

Each facility must have spill kits appropriate for the pathogens being worked with and chemicals used.

14th October 2013

Document History

Produced By AHVLA (Hugh Simmons) Oct 2012